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Sea surface height, sea surface temperature, and chlorophyll-a as indicators for determining eddy in Indonesian waters

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ABSTRACT

Sea surface height, sea surface temperature, and chlorophyll-a are parameters that can identify and monitor the presence and characteristics of eddies more accurately in the complex and dynamic waters of Indonesia. The identification and monitoring of eddies are important for understanding ocean variability and its implications for marine ecosystems. The objective of this study is to determine the distribution and characteristics of eddies in Indonesian waters. The data used were obtained from HYCOM (Hybrid Coordinate Ocean Model). The study area covered Indonesian waters with coordinates 6°N - 11°S and 95°E - 141.5°E, then processed using MATLAB software. Eddy detection was performed using the Automated Eddy Detection (AED) method. Sea surface height, sea surface temperature, and chlorophyll-a data were calculated and overlaid with the eddy detection results. The results of the study show that the highest concentration of eddies occurs in the waters west of Sumatra, south of Java, and the Indian Ocean with 107 occurrences, and in the waters north of Papua and the Pacific Ocean with 101 occurrences. The average diameter of cyclonic eddies is 90.626 km and 95.834 km for anticyclonic eddies. The average SSH value was 0.547 m for cyclonic eddies and 0.644 m for anticyclonic eddies. The average temperature was 29.209 °C for cyclonic eddies and 29.356 °C for anticyclonic eddies. The average chlorophyll-a value is 0.069 mg/m³ for cyclonic eddies and 0.074 mg/m³ for anticyclonic eddies.

Keywords: Anticyclonic eddy, chlorophyll-a, cyclonic eddy, Indonesian waters, sea surface height, sea surface temperature

1. INTRODUCTION

Indonesian waters are located in a tropical region with two seasons, namely the East and West seasons [2]. The dynamics of Indonesian waters, especially at the surface layer, are strongly influenced by monsoon wind patterns and tides. Seasonal and annual variability in Indonesia is caused by changes in the direction and strength of the wind blowing over the waters following the Australia-Asia (Australasia) monsoon system, causing changes in water dynamics. The northwest monsoon occurs from December to February (west season) when maximum transport occurs and the southeast monsoon during June to August (east season) when maximum transport occurs [2-7]. Indonesian waters are also affected by global circulation such as the Indonesian Throughflow. Seasonally, the Indonesian Throughflow has an impact on the distribution of sea surface temperature in Indonesian waters, especially if there is a large pressure gradient between the Pacific Ocean and the Indian Ocean [1, 5]. In addition to having complex oceanographic dynamics and the influence of global circulation, Indonesian waters are affected by local phenomena such as eddies.

Eddy is a circular current separated from the main current, it can form in the ocean with spatial scales ranging from tens to hundreds of kilometers and temporal scales ranging from weeks to months [8-11]. There are two types of eddy based on its diameter, namely submesoscale and mesoscale [13]. The submesoscale type has a diameter of tens of kilometers, while the mesoscale type can reach 50-200 km. Eddy currents move around to form circular structures, both to the right (anticyclonic) and left (cyclonic), which play a role in the distribution of energy, nutrients and heat in the ocean. Sea Surface Height (SSH), Sea Surface Temperature (SST), and Chlorophyll-a concentration are three important oceanographic parameters used as indicators in detecting the presence of eddy currents in Indonesian waters.

SSH can reflect the dynamics of water mass movement, the presence of sea surface height anomalies, signaling the presence of eddy. In a cyclonic eddy, the SSH tends to be lower than its surroundings, while in an anticyclonic eddy it is higher. SSH is a key parameter in detecting the presence of an eddy through satellite altimetry data. A cyclonic eddy is characterized by a decrease in sea level (depression), while an anticyclonic eddy shows an increase (elevation). These SSH patterns reflect the vertical motion of seawater, where cyclonic eddies trigger upwelling and anticyclonic eddies trigger downwelling. Using spatially and temporally reconstructed SSH images, the presence and trajectory of eddies can be mapped.

SST varies spatially and temporally and the influencing factors are very complex, but in the waters of the Indonesian Archipelago, the dominant influencing factors are local monsoon winds and water mass mixing due to tides [12]. SST correlates with SSH in indicating eddy thermal structure. Cyclonic eddies bring water from the cooler lower layers to the surface, resulting in a decrease in temperature at the center of the eddy. In contrast, an anticyclonic eddy raises warm water from the surface to the center of the eddy, causing an increase in temperature. Therefore, sea surface temperature anomalies can be used as a supporting indicator in eddy identification.

As a biological indicator, chlorophyll-a concentration reflects the primary productivity of the ocean. A cyclonic eddy that triggers upwelling will increase the availability of nutrients at the surface, thus promoting phytoplankton growth and increasing chlorophyll-a concentration. In contrast, in anticyclonic eddies, chlorophyll-a concentrations tend to decrease due to the downwelling process. Chlorophyll-a distribution patterns from satellite data can complement SSH and SST analysis in confirming the presence of eddy currents. Cyclonic eddies are

characterized by an up ward circulation flow pattern at the center, causing an increase in nutrient input. Meanwhile, the anticyclonic eddy is characterized by the accumulation of warm water mass, chlorophyll-a, and nutrient enrichment at the outer boundary of the eddy [14]. By combining these three parameters, researchers can more accurately identify and monitor the presence and characteristics of eddies in Indonesia's complex and dynamic waters. Identifying and monitoring eddies is important for understanding ocean variability and its implications for marine ecosystems, especially in Indonesia's biodiversity waters.

2. METHODS

Sea surface height (SSH) data, sea surface temperature and chlorophyll-a data obtained from Copernicus in Indonesian waters with datasets from January – December 2016. Sea surface height, sea surface temperature, and chlorophyll-a data were calculated and overlaid with the eddy detection results. The study area includes Indonesian waters with coordinates 6°N - 11°S and 95°E – 141.5°E.

Figure 1. Research Location.

Eddy detection is basically divided into three, namely based on physical parameters, flow geometry, and the combination between the two parameters [15]. This method has a higher accuracy in eddy detection is to use a combination of both parameters, Automated Eddy Detection (AED) is an eddy detection method that uses both parameters [16]. Data processing produces eddy spatial distribution and statistical data consisting of eddy center point position, eddy spatial frequency, radius, and eddy type. Daily SSH, temperature, chlorophyll-a data were averaged monthly at the surface. Furthermore, SSH, temperature, and SSH data are overlaid

horizontally with eddy detection data and the values of SSH, temperature, chlorophyll-a at the eddy center point and its surroundings are sought. SSH, temperature, chlorophyll-a parameters are used as supporting data in data analysis on eddy characteristics. To find out the monthly average value using the average formula (mean) as follows:

$$X = \sum Xi/n$$

Description:

- X : mean
- $\sum Xi$: The sum of each data
- N : Number of data

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3. 1. Eddy Detection

Current data was used to detect eddy using the AED method in Indonesian waters in 2016. Eddy detection results are shown in Figure 2. Eddy will be divided into two types distinguished by the color of the circle, namely the circle with red color is cyclonic eddy type (SE) and the circle with black color is anticyclonic type (AE). The center point of the eddy will be marked with a black dot in the center of the circle. There are two types of eddy direction movement: cyclonic and anticyclonic.

The eddy movement is different between the Northern Hemisphere (NE) and the Southern Hemisphere (SS). In the BBU, the eddy movement whose direction is counterclockwise is called cyclonic eddy and whose direction is clockwise is called anticyclonic eddy, while the BBS is the opposite, the eddy whose direction is clockwise is called cyclonic eddy and which is counterclockwise is called anticyclonic eddy [17].

Figure 2. Eddy Visualization using the AED Method.

In Indonesian waters there are several major water mass flows that flow throughout the year. These water masses are South Java Current (SJC) marked in red, South Equatorial Current (SEC) marked in yellow, Indonesian Throughflow marked in blue, Papua Coastal Current (NGCC) marked in black, and North Equatorial Current (NEC) marked in ash.

3. 2. Distribution of Eddy

Based on the results of the detection of the number of eddy formed in 2016 as many as 578 events with 302 is cyclonic eddy and 276 is anticyclonic eddy. The number of eddies in Indonesian waters each month can be seen in the table. December is the month with the most eddy occurrences, totaling 61 events, while August is the month with the least eddy occurrences, totaling 38 events. The average diameter of the eddy formed in Indonesian waters ranges from 8.13 - 622.5 km. Eddy with a diameter below 50 km is a type of submesoscale eddy, eddy with a diameter of 50-200 km is a mesoscale eddy, and eddy with a diameter measuring more than 250 km is a giant eddy.

Table 1. Number and Diameter of Eddies Formed.

Month to	Number of Eddy			Diameter		
	SE	AE	Total	Min	Max	Average
1	28	28	56	8.44	187.87	81.04
2	23	20	43	21.56	407.82	107.39
3	30	25	55	8.13	321.03	89.20
4	27	22	49	23.27	272.37	84.79
5	24	18	42	37.37	229.58	104.77
6	17	25	42	21.97	256.66	97.44
7	21	24	45	12.51	357.93	92.58
8	20	18	38	27.96	270.53	80.64
9	22	20	42	32.94	435.96	100.08
10	27	24	51	28.01	466.57	101.07
11	24	30	54	29.81	622.50	99.59
12	39	22	61	25.85	227.76	80.12
Total	302	276	578			

In the waters north of Papua to the Pacific Ocean, 101 eddy events were formed with 48 cyclonic types and 53 anticyclonic types. The diameter formed when the cyclonic eddy ranged from 88.70 - 229.37 km with an average diameter of 125.06. While when the anticyclonic eddy ranges from 56.12 - 194.39 km with an average diameter of 116.05 km. In general, eddies can occur due to strong current systems. Eddy that always occurs throughout the year, these waters are known as Halmahera Eddy and Mindanao Eddy. Halmahera eddy can occur due to collision between NGCC and topography in Halmahera region, while Mindanao eddy occurs due to collision between NEC and Mindanao current.

In the waters west of Sumatra, South of Java, to the Indian Ocean, 179 eddy events were formed with 104 cyclonic types and 75 anticyclonic types. The diameter formed when the cyclonic eddy ranged from 51.53 - 129.13 km with an average diameter of 90.98 km. While when the anticyclonic eddy ranges from 57.59 - 146.18 km with an average diameter of 120.08 km.

Southern waters are famous for the formation of many eddy because of the complex current system, the current system is one of the causes of eddy [18]. Almost every year eddy can occur in the southern waters of Java to the Indian Ocean due to the influence of the Arlindo APJ-AKS flow meeting which has a different direction. This difference in current direction can cause baroclinic imbalance so that it can create an eddy.

In the Sulawesi Sea, Makassar Strait, Flores Sea, 69 eddy events were formed with 25 cyclonic types and 44 anticyclonic types. The diameter formed when the cyclonic eddy ranges from 54.92 - 254.30 km with an average diameter of 133.96 km. While when the anticyclonic eddy ranges from 51.36 - 187.87 km with an average diameter of 86.31 km. Eddy in these waters is formed due to the shape of the topography and current system, especially Arlindo. The main door of Arlindo is the waters of the Sulawesi Sea and the Makassar Strait.

In the Banda Sea, Maluku Sea, Halmahera Sea, and Seram Sea, 104 eddy events were formed with 55 cyclonic types and 49 anticyclonic types. The diameter formed when the cyclonic eddy ranged from 44.43 - 115.24 km with an average diameter of 77.10 km. While when the anticyclonic eddy ranges from 49.11 - 84.05 km with an average diameter of 73.59 km. Eddy occurs in these waters because these waters have a topography that describes the islands, making the current system can turn directions.

In the Arafura Sea, Timor Sea, and Sawu Sea, 38 eddy events were formed with 21 cyclonic types and 17 anticyclonic types. The diameter formed when the cyclonic eddy ranged from 48.63 - 78.01 km with an average diameter of 64.98 km. While when the anticyclonic eddy ranges from 36.85 - 121.14 km with an average diameter of 81.38 km. The occurrence of eddy in these waters is caused by the meeting of Arlindo originating from the Banda Sea and passing south of Papua through the Timor Sea and Arafura Sea. Currents in the Arafura and Timor Waters experience a lot of current rotation both counterclockwise (anticyclonic) and clockwise (cyclonic). This is due to the deflection of the current direction so that there is a recirculation of currents in the southeast of Tanimbar Island and southeast of Timor Island. The meeting between Arlindo water masses brought from the Seram Sea and Banda Sea also causes turbulence to form a counterclockwise recirculation.

In the Java Sea, only 4 eddy events were formed with a cyclonic type. The diameter ranged from 53.38 - 123.76 km with an average diameter of 76.84 km. Eddy in the Java Sea can occur in transitional seasons and is influenced by sea level anomalies and wind speed. In the west and east seasons no eddy is formed in the Java Sea due to constant winds. Low values

of wind stress and Ekman transport show an indication of a weak eddy that occurs in the Java Sea. Eddy formed in the Java Sea is classified into the sub-mesoscale category.

In the South China Sea to the Karimata Strait, 34 eddy events were formed with a cyclonic type of 20 and an anticyclonic type of 14. The diameter formed when the cyclonic eddy ranged from 53.34 - 159.12 km with an average diameter of 100.62 km. While when the anticyclonic eddy ranges from 32.81 - 128.19 km with an average diameter of 70.84 km. In the southern waters of the South China Sea, cyclonic and anticyclonic eddy are found with different depths in the rainy season and dry season [19].

In the Outer Indonesian Waters such as the Andaman Sea to the Malacca Strait, 22 eddy events were formed with 7 cyclonic types and 15 anticyclonic types. The diameter formed when the cyclonic eddy ranged from 51.07 - 123.99 km with an average diameter of 98.54 km. While when the anticyclonic eddy ranges from 31.45 - 145.43 km with an average diameter of 96.11.

In the Sulu Sea, 27 eddy events were formed with 18 cyclonic types and 9 anticyclonic types. The diameter formed when the cyclonic eddy ranged from 37.99 - 108.64 km with an average diameter of 80.75 km. While when the anticyclonic eddy ranges from 53.31 - 132.72 km with an average diameter of 76.27 km.

3. 3. Eddy and Sea Surface Height (SSH)

SSH at the center point has a low value due to the influence of the Coriolis force which is High SSH values will be marked in red and low SSH values will be marked in blue. In general, the SSH value in Indonesian waters ranges from 0.1 - 1 m. Sea surface height can be used as an indicator in determining the type of eddy because it is closely related to the occurrence of upwelling and downwelling phenomena. Low SSH values are associated with upwelling phenomena or when a cyclonic eddy occurs, while areas with high SSH values are generally associated with downwelling areas or when an anticyclonic eddy occurs.

When a cyclonic eddy occurs, it deflects the direction of the current out of the eddy center point, causing a divergence process that creates a vacuum of water mass at the eddy center point. Conversely, in the anticyclonic eddy, the SSH value at the eddy center point has a higher value because the Coriolis force deflects the current direction towards the eddy center point causing the convergence process so that there is a buildup of water mass at the eddy center point. The average value of SSH at the eddy center point in a year is 0.55 m during cyclonic eddy and 0.64 m during anticyclonic eddy. SSH value at the eddy center point in Indonesian waters during 2016.

In the waters north of Papua to the Pacific Ocean in January to April, the SSH was lower than other waters with values ranging from 0.1 - 0.6 m. In May to October it continued to increase. From May to October, it continued to increase and peaked in November with a value of 0.85 m. During the cyclonic eddy, the SSH value at the center point of the eddy ranged from 0.17 - 0.60 m with an average value of 0.48 m. The low value occurs in February and the highest value in September. During the anticyclonic eddy, the SSH value at the eddy center point ranged from 0.53 - 0.78 m with an average value of 0.65 m. The low value occurred in March and the highest value in October. When the cyclonic eddy in February to September increased, while when the anticyclonic eddy from January to June increased but decreased until August and increased again in November.

In the waters west of Sumatra, South of Java, to the Indian Ocean, SSH values tend to be low throughout the year compared to other waters ranging from 0.3 - 0.7 m. April to June the western waters of Sumatra experienced an increase in SSH values of 0.5 - 0.75 m. Meanwhile,

the waters south of Java to the Indian Ocean tend not to experience significant changes in SSH. During the cyclonic eddy, the SSH value at the eddy center point ranges from 0.41 - 0.59 m with an average of 0.48 m. The low value occurs in February and the low value occurs in June. The low value occurred in February and the highest value in July. During the anticyclonic eddy, the SSH value at the eddy center point ranged from 0.52 - 0.74 m with an average value of 0.60 m. The low value occurs in January and the highest value in June.

In the Sulawesi Sea, Makassar Strait, and Flores Sea have SSH values that do not experience significant changes throughout the year with values ranging from 0.5 - 0.8 m. In January to December the SSH value continues to increase but in July - August it decreases. In January to December the SSH value continues to increase but in July - August it decreases. SSH values at the eddy center point in the Sulawesi Sea, Makassar Strait, and Flores Sea. During the cyclonic eddy, the SSH value at the eddy center point ranged from 0.49 - 0.68 m with an average of 0.57 m.

The low value occurred in April and the low value occurred in August. The low value occurs in April and the highest value in August. During the anticyclonic eddy, the SSH value at the eddy center point ranged from 0.62 - 0.72 m with an average value of 0.68 m. The low value occurs in May and the highest value in September.

In the Banda Sea, Maluku Sea, Halmahera Sea, and Seram Sea also did not experience significant changes throughout the year in the value of SSH with a range between 0.5 - 0.7 m. January to December experienced an increase in SSH values and the highest values in November to December. SSH values at the eddy center point in the Banda Sea, Maluku Sea, Halmahera Sea, and Seram Sea.

During the cyclonic eddy, the SSH value at the center point of the eddy ranged from 0.51 - 0.68 m with an average of 0.58 m. The low value occurs in January and the highest value in November. During the anticyclonic eddy, the SSH value at the eddy center point ranged from 0.54 - 0.71 m with an average value of 0.63 m. The low value occurs in January and the highest value in November.

In the Arafura Sea, Timor Sea, and Sawu Sea, the SSH value also did not experience significant changes. From January to December, they have SSH values in the range of 0.5 - 0.8 m. SSH value at the center point of the eddy in the Arafura Sea, Timor Sea, and Sawu Sea. During the cyclonic eddy, the SSH value at the eddy center point ranges from 0.47 to 0.66 m with an average of 0.53 m. The low value occurs in April and the highest value in December. During the anticyclonic eddy, the SSH value at the eddy center point ranges from 0.51 - 0.72 m with an average value of 0.63 m. The low value occurs in April and the highest value in December.

In the Java Sea, the SSH value also did not experience significant changes. From January to December, the SSH value ranges from 0.6 - 0.8 m. SSH value at the eddy center point in the Java Sea. In the Java Sea only a cyclonic eddy is formed with SSH values at the eddy center point ranging from 0.66 - 0.71 m with an average of 0.68 m. Low values occur in April and high values occur in November.

In the South China Sea to the Karimata Strait SSH tends to have a high value of 0.6 - 1 m. In January to March the SSH value is higher compared to other waters. In April SSH decreased and increased again until the peak in December. SSH value at the eddy center point in the South China Sea to the Karimata Strait. During the cyclonic eddy, the SSH value at the eddy center point ranges from 0.63 - 0.73 m with an average of 0.68 m. The low value occurs in May and the highest value in December.

Figure 3. Sea Surface Height in Indonesian Waters in a Year.

During the anticyclonic eddy, the SSH value at the eddy center point ranged from 0.70 - 0.88 m with an average value of 0.77 m. The low value occurs in May and the highest value in November.

In the Andaman Sea to the Malacca Strait, the SSH value ranges from 0.4 - 0.8 m. The lowest SSH occurs in February and the highest in June. SSH values in the Andaman Sea to the Malacca Strait. During the cyclonic eddy, the SSH value at the center point of the eddy ranges from 0.38 - 0.69 m with an average of 0.56 m. The low value occurs in April and the highest value in June. The low value occurs in April and the highest value in June. During the anticyclonic eddy, the SSH value at the eddy center point ranged from 0.52 - 0.82 m with an average value of 0.66 m. The low value occurred in February and the highest value in June.

In the Sulu Sea, SSH values tend not to have significant changes with a range of 0.6 - 0.8m. The highest SSH value occurs in October and the lowest occurs in April. During the cyclonic eddy, the SSH value at the eddy center point ranges from 0.60 - 0.74 m with an average of 0.66 m. The low value occurs in January and the highest value in April. The lowest value occurred in January and the highest value in September. During the anticyclonic eddy, the SSH value at the eddy center point ranges from 0.65 - 0.77 m with an average value of 0.71 m.

The low value occurred in April and the highest value in August.

3. 4. Eddy and Sea Surface Temperature (SST)

High temperature values will be marked in red and low temperature values will be marked in blue. In general, temperature values in Indonesian waters range from 26 - 32 °C. Temperature variations in Indonesian waters follow seasonal changes. The main factor affecting sea surface temperature is sunlight intensity. In addition, sea surface temperature is influenced by several meteorological factors such as rainfall, evaporation, air temperature, wind speed, air humidity, and cloud conditions. Environmental conditions such as surface currents, upwelling and divergence and convergence along the coastline also affect sea temperatures [20].

Temperature in a body of water can also be used as an indicator of eddy determination. Generally, when a cyclonic eddy occurs, the temperature at the center point of the eddy will look lower than the surrounding temperature, while when an anticyclonic eddy occurs, the temperature at the center point of the eddy will be higher than the surrounding temperature. The average value of temperature at the eddy center point in a year is 29.21 °C during cyclonic eddy and 29.36 °C during anticyclonic eddy.

In the waters north of Papua to the Pacific Ocean, the temperature continues to increase from January to December ranging from 27.5 - 30.5 °C. The highest temperature is in June and the lowest in February. During the cyclonic eddy, the temperature value at the eddy center point ranges from 27.75 - 29.70 °C with an average of 29.13 °C. The lowest temperature is in February and the highest temperature is in July. During the eddy anticyclonic, the temperature value at the eddy center point ranges from 28.27 - 29.81 °C with an average of 29.30 °C. The lowest temperature is in February and the highest temperature is in October.

In the waters west of Sumatra, South of Java, to the Indian Ocean in January to May experienced an increase in temperature ranging from 28.5 - 30.5 °C. In June to December, it decreases in the range of 26-30 °C. The highest temperature occurs in May and the lowest temperature occurs in August. During the cyclonic eddy, the temperature value at the eddy center point ranged from 28.41 - 30.22 °C with an average of 29.14 °C. The lowest temperature was in August and the highest temperature was in March.

During the eddy anticyclonic, the temperature value at the eddy center point ranges from 28.66 - 30.10 °C with an average of 29.35 °C. The lowest temperature is in November and the highest temperature is in March.

In the Sulawesi Sea, Makassar Strait, Flores Sea in January to June experienced an increase in temperature ranging from 28.5 - 30.5 °C. In July to December experienced a decrease ranging from 28 - 29.5 °C. The lowest temperature occurs in August and the highest in May. During the cyclonic eddy, the temperature value at the eddy center point ranged from 28.53 - 29.84 °C with an average of 29.27 °C. The lowest temperature is in February and the highest temperature is in June. During the eddy anticyclonic, the temperature value at the eddy center point ranges from 28.91 - 29.73 °C with an average of 29.28 °C. The lowest temperature is in February and the highest temperature is in May.

In the Banda Sea, Maluku Sea, Halmahera Sea, and Seram Sea in January to May, the increase ranged from 28 - 30 °C, in June to August it decreased ranging from 26 - 29 °C, in September to December the temperature increased again ranging from 28 - 30.5 °C. The lowest temperature occurs in August and the lowest temperature occurs in November. During the cyclonic eddy, the temperature value at the eddy center point ranges from 27.76 - 30.23 °C with an average of 29.18 °C. The lowest temperature is in August and the highest temperature is in May. During the anticyclonic eddy, the temperature value at the eddy center point ranges from 28.72 - 30.01 °C with an average of 29.43 °C. The lowest temperature is in July and the highest temperature is in May.

In the Arafura Sea, Timor Sea, and Sawu Sea from January to March, the increase ranges from 29 - 31 °C, from April to August, the decrease ranges from 26 - 30.5 °C, from September to December, the increase ranges from 27 - 31 °C. During the cyclonic eddy, the temperature value at the eddy center point ranges from 27.67 - 30.41 °C with an average of 29.50 °C. The lowest temperature is in August and the highest temperature is in February. During the anticyclonic eddy, the temperature value at the eddy center point ranges from 27.23 - 30.44 °C with an average of 29.41 °C. The lowest temperature is in August and the highest temperature is in March.

In the Java Sea, the temperature value from January to May increases around 29 - 31 °C, from June to September it decreases around 28 - 30 °C, from October to December it increases around 29 - 31 °C. In the Java Sea, only a cyclonic eddy is formed with the temperature value at the eddy center point ranging from 29.59 - 30.08 °C with an average of 29.78 °C. Low values occur in November and high values occur in April.

In the South China Sea to the Karimata Strait has a temperature value ranging from 26 - 31 °C. In January to May, it increases around 28 - 31 °C, in June to December it decreases around 26 - 30 °C. During the cyclonic eddy, the temperature value at the eddy center point ranges from 27.55 - 30.05 °C with an average of 28.73 °C. The lowest temperature is in February and the highest temperature is in May. During the anticyclonic eddy, the temperature value at the eddy center point ranges from 27.84 - 30.05 °C with an average of 29.05 °C. The lowest temperature in February and the highest temperature in April.

In the Andaman Sea and Malacca Strait, the temperature value ranges from 28 - 31 °C. In the months of January to May, it increases in the range of 29 - 31 °C. In June to December it decreases in the range of 28 - 31 °C. During the cyclonic eddy, the temperature value at the eddy center point ranges from 28.60 - 30.54 °C with an average of 29.65 °C. The lowest temperature is in November and the highest temperature is in April.

Figure 4. Temperature in Indonesian Waters in a Year.

During anticyclonic eddy, the temperature value at the eddy center point ranges from 28.23 - 30.54 °C with an average of 29.01 °C. The lowest temperature is in October and the highest temperature is in May.

In the Sulu Sea, the temperature ranges from 28 - 31°C. In the months of January to July, it ranges from 29 - 31 °C. In August to December, it decreases in the range of 28 - 31 °C. During the cyclonic eddy, the temperature value at the eddy center point ranges from 27.61 - 29.72 °C with an average of 28.80 °C. The lowest temperature is in February and the highest temperature is in June. During the anticyclonic eddy, the temperature value at the eddy center point ranges from 27.98 - 30.19 °C with an average of 29.18 °C. The lowest temperature was in March and the highest temperature was in May.

3. 5. Eddy and Chlorophyll-a

In the waters north of Papua to the Pacific Ocean, chlorophyll-a values range from 0 - 0.25 mg/m³. During the cyclonic eddy, the chlorophyll-a value at the eddy center point ranges from 0.053 - 0.114 mg/m³ with an average of 0.067 mg/m³. The lowest chlorophyll-a in August and the highest chlorophyll-a in January. During the anticyclonic eddy, Chlorophyll-a values at the eddy center point ranged from 0.053 - 0.114 mg/m³ with an average of 0.072 mg/m³. Chlorophyll-a is lowest in December and highest in January.

In the waters west of Sumatra, South of Java, to the Indian Ocean has chlorophyll-a values with a range of 0 - 0.2 mg/m³. During the cyclonic eddy, the chlorophyll-a value at the eddy center point ranges from 0.055 - 0.070 mg/m³ with an average of 0.063 mg/m³. Chlorophyll-a was lowest in June and highest in November. During the anticyclonic eddy, Chlorophyll-a values at the eddy center point ranged from 0.052 - 0.100 mg/m³ with an average of 0.066 mg/m³. The lowest chlorophyll-a in July and the highest chlorophyll-a in December.

In the Sulawesi Sea, Makassar Strait, and Flores Sea have chlorophyll-a values with a range of 0.05 - 0.1 mg/m³. During the cyclonic eddy, chlorophyll-a values at the eddy center point ranged from 0.070 - 0.078 mg/m³ with an average of 0.072 mg/m³. Chlorophyll-a was lowest in May and highest in February. During the anticyclonic eddy, Chlorophyll-a values at the eddy center point ranged from 0.071 - 0.092 mg/m³ with an average of 0.082 mg/m³. Chlorophyll-a was lowest in January and highest in February.

In the Banda Sea, Maluku Sea, Halmahera Sea, and Seram Sea, chlorophyll-a values range from 0.05 - 0.1 mg/m³. During the cyclonic eddy, chlorophyll-a values at the eddy center point ranged from 0.070 - 0.076 mg/m³ with an average of 0.073 mg/m³. Chlorophyll-a was lowest in February and highest in June. During the anticyclonic eddy, Chlorophyll-a values at the eddy center point ranged from 0.068 - 0.079 mg/m³ with an average of 0.073 mg/m³. Chlorophyll-a was lowest in September and highest in April.

In the Arafura Sea, Timor Sea, Sawu Sea, chlorophyll-a values range from 0.05 - 0.4 mg/m³. During the cyclonic eddy, the chlorophyll-a value at the eddy center point ranges from 0.066 - 0.079 mg/m³ with an average of 0.073 mg/m³. Chlorophyll-a was lowest in September and highest in January. During the anticyclonic eddy, Chlorophyll-a values at the eddy center point ranged from 0.069 - 0.080 mg/m³ with an average of 0.074 mg/m³. Chlorophyll-a was lowest in September and highest in August.

In the Java Sea has chlorophyll-a values with a range of 0.1 - 0.4 mg/m³. In January, only a cyclonic eddy was formed with chlorophyll-a values at the center of the eddy ranging from 0.103 - 0.118 mg/m³ with an average of 0.110 mg/m³. Chlorophyll-a is lowest in November and highest in April.

The South China Sea has chlorophyll-a values with a range of 0.1 - 0.3 mg/m³. During the cyclonic eddy, the chlorophyll-a value at the eddy center point ranges from 0.064 - 0.085 mg/m³ with an average of 0.076 mg/m³. Chlorophyll-a was lowest in June and highest in November. During the anticyclonic eddy, Chlorophyll-a values at the eddy center point ranged from 0.066 - 0.104 mg/m³ with an average of 0.076 mg/m³. Chlorophyll-a is lowest in May and highest in October. In the Andaman Sea to the Malacca Strait, chlorophyll-a values range from 0 - 0.2 mg/m³. During the cyclonic eddy, chlorophyll-a values at the eddy center point ranged from 0.068 - 0.114 mg/m³ with an average of 0.082 mg/m³. Chlorophyll-a was lowest in June and highest in November. During the anticyclonic eddy, Chlorophyll-a values at the eddy center point ranged from 0.029 - 0.122 mg/m³ with an average of 0.089 mg/m³. Chlorophyll-a is lowest in March and highest in October. In the Sulu Sea has chlorophyll-a values with a range of 0.05 - 0.1 mg/m³. During the cyclonic eddy, chlorophyll-a values at the eddy center point ranged from 0.069 - 0.079 mg/m³ with an average of 0.074 mg/m³. Chlorophyll-a was lowest in January and highest in April. During the anticyclonic eddy, Chlorophyll-a values at the eddy center point ranged from 0.071 - 0.079 mg/m³ with an average of 0.075 mg/m³. Chlorophyll-a was lowest in August and highest in April.

Eddies have a direct influence on the distribution and concentration of chlorophyll-a, which is a key indicator of phytoplankton productivity. Cyclonic eddies are usually associated with upwelling (the lifting of water masses from below to the surface), which brings nutrients from the deep layers to the surface. Significant increases in chlorophyll-a concentration are detected at the center or inner side of cyclonic eddies due to nutrient upwelling [21]. Anticyclonic eddies are generally associated with downwelling (the sinking of surface water masses), which can cause a decrease in chlorophyll-a concentration. However, in some cases, the outer edges of anticyclonic eddies exhibit high chlorophyll concentrations due to mixing or horizontal convergence [22]. The influence of eddies on chlorophyll-a is highly dependent on geographical location, season, and background oceanographic conditions [23]. In tropical regions such as Indonesia, the interaction between eddies and seasonal currents (Indonesian Throughflow) also influences the distribution of chlorophyll-a in complex ways.

4. CONCLUSIONS

- 1) The distribution of eddy mostly occurs in open waters, such as western Sumatra, southern Java, to the Indian Ocean with 107 events and northern Papua to the Pacific Ocean with 101 events. The average diameter of the eddy is 90.626 km for cyclonic eddy and 95.834 km for anticyclonic eddy.
- 2) The average SSH value is 0.547 m for cyclonic eddy and 0.644 for anticyclonic eddy. Mean temperature value 29.209 °C for cyclonic eddy and 29.356 °C anticyclonic eddy. Average chlorophyll-a value of 0.069 mg/m³ for cyclonic eddy and 0.074 mg/m³ for anticyclonic eddy.

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